

A NOTE ON A CONJECTURE OF ERDŐS, GRAHAM, AND
SPENCER

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Abstract

Let $1 \leq a_1 \leq a_2 \leq \dots \leq a_s$ be integers with $\sum_{i=1}^s 1/a_i \geq n + 9/31$. In this paper, we prove that this sum can be decomposed into n parts so that all partial sums are greater than or equal to 1.

1. Introduction

Erdős, Graham and Spencer [1] posed the conjecture that if $1 \leq a_1 \leq a_2 \leq \dots \leq a_s$ are integers with $\sum_{i=1}^s 1/a_i < n - 1/30$, then this sum can be decomposed into n parts so that all partial sums are less than or equal to 1. A counterexample given by Guo [4], as shown by $a_1 = 2, a_2 = a_3 = 3, a_4 = 4, a_5 = \dots = a_{11n-12} = 11$, tells us that we should replace $1/30$ by $5/132$ or a larger quantity.

On the other hand, Sándor [3] proved that the Erdős-Graham-Spencer conjecture is true for $\sum_{i=1}^s 1/a_i \leq n - 1/2$, and recently, Chen [5], Fang and Chen [2] replace $1/2$ by $1/3$ and $2/7$, respectively.

In this paper, instead of improving the bound, we consider the following similar problem.

Problem 1. Find the least positive number $\eta^+ = \eta^+(n)$ such that when $1 \leq a_1 \leq a_2 \leq \dots \leq a_s$ are integers with $\sum_{i=1}^s 1/a_i \geq n + \eta^+$, then this sum can be decomposed into n parts so that all partial sums are ≥ 1 .

We get the following result.

Theorem 2. *Let n given, and let $\eta^+ = \eta^+(n)$ be defined as in Problem 1. Then*

$$\frac{5}{156} < \eta^+ \leq \frac{9}{31}.$$

Let $\eta^- = \eta^-(n)$ be the least positive number such that when $1 \leq a_1 \leq a_2 \leq \dots \leq a_s$ are integers with $\sum_{i=1}^s 1/a_i \leq n - \eta^-$, then this sum can be decomposed into n parts so that all partial sums are less than or equal to 1. By the results of Guo [4], Fang and Chen [2] we know $\frac{5}{132} < \eta^- \leq \frac{2}{7}$. We have the following problem.

Problem 3. Is there any relationship between η^- and η^+ ?

In order to prove the theorem, we only need to consider those sequences such that each term is more than 1 and no partial sum (of two or more terms) is the inverse of a positive integer; otherwise, we may replace the partial sum by the inverse of the integer. We call a sequence $1 \leq a_1 \leq a_2 \leq \dots \leq a_s$ *primitive* if no partial sum of $\sum_{i=1}^s 1/a_i$ is the inverse of a positive integer. In this paper, we consider multisets (i.e., sets with repetitions allowed) of positive integers. Let A be a multiset, and $T(A) = \sum_{i=1}^s 1/a_i$, then A is primitive if $1 \notin A$ and there is no multisubset A_1 of A with the cardinality of $A_1 \geq 2$ and $T(A_1)^{-1}$ being an integer.

2. Notation

For a multiset A and a positive real number x , let $m_A(a)$ denote the multiplicity of a in A , let $m(A)$ denote the cardinality of A and let

$$A(x) = \{a : a \in A, a < x\}.$$

For example, if $A = \{2, 3, 3, 4, 5, 5\}$, $B = \{3, 4, 5\}$, then $m_A(1) = 0$, $m_A(2) = 1$, $m_A(3) = 2$, $m_A(4) = 1$, $m_A(5) = 2$, $m(A) = 6$, and

$$A(4) = \{2, 3, 3\}, \quad A \setminus B = \{2, 3, 5\}.$$

With this notation, we say that A has an n^+ -*quasiunit partition* if A can be decomposed into n multisubsets A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n , with $T(A_i) \geq 1$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$) and $m_{A_1}(a) + m_{A_2}(a) + \dots + m_{A_n}(a) = m_A(a)$ for all integers a . In the following discussion, if we write $A = \cup_{i=1}^n A_i$, we mean that $\sum_{i=1}^n m_{A_i}(a) = m_A(a)$ for every $a \in A$, and, without loss of generality, we assume $n \geq 2$.

3. Preliminaries

Similar to Lemma 2 of [5], we have the following lemma.

Lemma 4. *Let η be a positive real number and n a positive integer. If for any positive integer $k \leq n$, any finite primitive multiset A with $T(A) \geq k + \eta$ has a k^+ -quasiunit partition, then any finite multiset A with $T(A) \geq n + \eta$ has an n^+ -quasiunit partition.*

Proof. Let A be a finite multiset of positive integers. From Lemma 1 of [5] we know there exists an effective constructible finite primitive multiset A' and a nonnegative integer k such that $T(A) = k + T(A')$, and then the lemma follows. \square

Lemma 5. *Let η be a positive real number and let A be a finite multiset with $T(A) = n + \eta$ and $A((n-1)/\eta) = B_1 \cup B_2 \cup \dots \cup B_n$, and such that $\sum_{i=1}^n m_{B_i}(a) = m_A(a)$ for all integers a . Then A has an n^+ -quasiunit partition if one of the following conditions holds:*

- (i) $T(B_i) \geq 1$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$;
- (ii) $T(B_i) \leq 1 + \frac{\eta}{n-1}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$;
- (iii) $T(A(\frac{n-1}{\eta})) \leq n - \frac{2}{7}$.

Proof. (i) It is obvious in this case.

(ii) If for every $1 \leq i \leq n$, one has $T(B_i) \geq 1$, then it is just case (i). If there exists $1 \leq j \leq n$, such that $T(B_j) < 1$, then

$$T(\cup_{i=1}^s B_i) = \sum_{i=1}^s T(B_i) < n + \frac{(n-1)\eta}{n-1} = n + \eta = T(A).$$

Thus $A \setminus A((n-1)/\eta) \neq \emptyset$. Add $a \in A \setminus A((n-1)/\eta)$ to B_j . If $T(B_j) \geq 1$, we have $1 \leq T(B_j) < 1 + \eta/(n-1)$. Otherwise, repeat this process for $A \setminus A((n-1)/\eta) \setminus \{a\}$. Since A is a finite set, we may get $T(B_i) \geq 1$ after finite steps, and then the result follows.

(iii) It follows from (ii) and the result of [2]. \square

Let $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_r\}$, $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_s\}$ be multisets. We write $F(B) \geq F(C)$ if $r \geq s$ and $c_i \geq b_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq s$.

Lemma 6. *Let B, C be multisets with $F(B) \geq F(C)$ and $\mu_i > 0$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. If $B = \cup_{i=1}^n B_i$ and $T(B_i) \leq \mu_i$, then C can be decomposed into $C = \cup_{i=1}^n C_i$ with $T(C_i) \leq \mu_i$.*

Proof. Let $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_r\}$, $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_s\}$ be multisets and $c_i \geq b_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq s$. Let $B_i \cap \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s\} = \{b_{i_1}, b_{i_2}, \dots, b_{i_k}\}$ and put $C_i = \{c_{i_1}, c_{i_2}, \dots, c_{i_k}\}$. Then $T(C_i) \leq T(B_i) \leq \mu_i$. \square

4. The Proof

We are now ready to give the proof of Theorem 2.

Proof. We begin by proving $\eta^+ > 5/156$. Let $n \geq 2$ and

$$a_1 = 2, \quad a_2 = a_3 = 3, \quad a_4 = 4, \quad a_5 = \dots = a_{13n-14} = 13;$$

then

$$\sum_{i=1}^{13n-14} \frac{1}{a_i} = n + \frac{5}{156}.$$

Let $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{13n-14}\} = B_1 \cup B_2 \cup \dots \cup B_n$. Then there exists $1 \leq j \leq n$ such that $T(B_j) < 1$, which yields $\eta^+ > 5/156$. In fact, suppose that $T(B_j) \geq 1$ for every $1 \leq j \leq n$. Without loss of generality, we assume $2 \in B_1$.

If $\{3, 3\} \subset B_1$, then

$$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3} = 1 + \frac{1}{6} > 1 + \frac{5}{156},$$

which is impossible.

If $3 \in B_1$, then

$$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} = 1 + \frac{1}{12} > 1 + \frac{5}{156},$$

and we know that $4 \notin B_1$; thus

$$T(B_1) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{r}{13},$$

which is impossible since

$$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{13} = \frac{77}{78} < 1, \quad \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{3}{13} = 1 + \frac{5}{78} > 1 + \frac{5}{156}.$$

Therefore we have

$$T(B_1) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{r}{13},$$

which is also impossible since

$$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{6}{13} = \frac{25}{26} < 1, \quad \frac{1}{2} + \frac{7}{13} = 1 + \frac{1}{26} > 1 + \frac{5}{156}.$$

We have proved the left inequality in Theorem 2, and we proceed to prove the right inequality in it, that is, $\eta^+ \leq 9/31$.

By Lemma 4, we assume A is primitive with $T(A) \geq n + 9/31$. By Lemmas 3-5 in [2] and the proof of the main theorem in the same paper, we know that $T(A(31(n-1)/9)) \leq T(A(7(n-1)/2)) \leq n - 1/3$ for $n = 2, 3, 4$ and $n \geq 11$. Then from Lemma 5(iii), A has an n^+ - quasiunit partition.

To finish the proof, we treat the cases $5 \leq n \leq 10$. First we have the following equalities:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{6} &= \frac{1}{2}, & \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{12} &= \frac{1}{3}, & \frac{2}{5} + \frac{1}{10} &= \frac{1}{2}, & \frac{1}{5} + \frac{2}{15} &= \frac{1}{3}, \\ \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{20} &= \frac{1}{4}, & \frac{3}{7} + \frac{1}{14} &= \frac{1}{2}, & \frac{2}{7} + \frac{1}{21} &= \frac{1}{3}, & \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{24} &= \frac{1}{6}, \\ \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{18} &= \frac{1}{6}, & \frac{5}{11} + \frac{1}{22} &= \frac{1}{2}, & \frac{1}{15} + \frac{1}{30} &= \frac{1}{10}, & \frac{6}{13} + \frac{1}{26} &= \frac{1}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Since A is primitive, the two fractions in the left-hand side of each equality above cannot exist in $T(A)$ at the same time.

Below, the notation $b(v)$ in the multiset B means that $m_B(b) = v$.

(1) $n = 5$

Let $B = \{2, 3(2), 4, 5(4), 7(6), 8, 9(2), 11(10), 13(12)\}$; then $F(B) \geq F(A(124/9))$. By Lemma 5(ii) and Lemma 6, A has a 5^+ - quasiunit partition since $B = \cup_{i=1}^5 B_i$ with $B_1 = \{2, 3, 9(2)\}$, $B_2 = \{3, 4, 5(2), 13\}$, $B_3 = \{5(2), 7(4), 11\}$, $B_4 = \{7(2), 8, 11(7)\}$, $B_5 = \{11(2), 13(11)\}$ and $T(B_i) < 1 + \frac{9}{124}$ for $1 \leq i \leq 5$.

(2) $n = 6$

Let $B = \{2, 3(2), 4, 5(4), 7(6), 8, 9(2), 11(10), 12, 13(12), 15, 16, 17(16)\}$; then $F(B) \geq F(A(155/9))$. Let $B = \cup_{i=1}^6 B_i$ with $B_1 = \{2, 3, 9(2)\}$, $B_2 = \{3, 4, 17(8)\}$, $B_3 = \{5(4), 8, 15, 16\}$, $B_4 = \{7(6), 13, 17(2)\}$, $B_5 = \{11(9), 17(4)\}$, $B_6 = \{11, 13(11), 17(2)\}$. Then $T(B_i) < 1 + \frac{9}{155}$ for $1 \leq i \leq 6$, which implies that A has a 6^+ - quasiunit partition by Lemma 5 and Lemma 6.

(3) $n = 7, 8$

Let $B = \{2, 3(2), 4, 5(4), 7(6), 8, 9(2), 11(10), 13(12), 15, 16, 17(16), 19(18)\}$, $C = B \cup \{23(22)\}$. Then $B = \cup_{i=1}^7 B_i$, $C = \cup_{i=1}^8 C_i$ with $B_1 = \{2, 13(7)\}$, $B_2 = \{3(2), 4\}$, $B_3 = \{5(4), 11, 13(2)\}$, $B_4 = \{7(6), 9, 13\}$, $B_5 = \{11(9), 9, 19(2)\}$, $B_6 = \{8, 13(2), 15, 16, 17(2), 19\}$, $B_7 = \{17(4), 19(15)\}$, $C_1 = B_1$, $C_2 = B_2$, $C_3 = \{5(4), 13(3)\}$, $C_4 = \{7(6), 11(2)\}$, $C_5 = \{9(2), 11(8), 23(2)\}$, $C_6 = B_6$, $C_7 = B_7$, $C_8 = \{19(2), 23(20)\}$ and $T(B_i) < 1 + \frac{3}{62}$ for $1 \leq i \leq 7$, $T(C_i) \leq 1 + \frac{9}{217}$ for $1 \leq i \leq 8$. It is easy to see that $F(T(A(62/3))) \leq F(B)$ and $F(T(A(217/9))) \leq F(C)$. From Lemma 5(ii) and Lemma 6, we know that A has a 7^+ - quasiunit partition for $n = 7$ and an 8^+ - quasiunit partition for $n = 8$.

(4) $n = 9, 10$

Let $B = \{2, 3(2), 4, 5(4), 7(6), 8, 9(2), 11(10), 13(12), 15, 16, 17(16), 19(18), 23(22), 25(4), 27(2)\}$, $C = B \cup \{28, 29(28)\}$. Then $B = \cup_{i=1}^9 B_i$, $C = \cup_{i=1}^{10} C_i$ with $B_1 = \{2, 4, 8, 27(2)\}$, $B_2 = \{3(2), 9(2)\}$, $B_3 = \{5(4), 15\}$, $B_4 = \{7(6), 16\}$, $B_5 = \{11(10), 25(2)\}$, $B_6 = \{13(12), 25\}$, $B_7 = \{17(16), 25\}$, $B_8 = \{19(18)\}$, $B_9 = \{23(22)\}$, $C_1 = B_1 \cup \{28\}$, $C_i = B_i$ for $2 \leq i \leq 9$, $C_{10} = \{29(28)\}$, and for all i , $T(B_i), T(C_i)$ are less than 1. Since $F(T(A(248/9))) \leq F(B)$, $F(T(A(31))) \leq F(C)$, from Lemma 5(ii) and Lemma 6, we get $\eta^+ \leq \frac{9}{31}$ for $n = 9, 10$. \square

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References

- [1] P. Erdős, R. Graham, *Old and New Problems and Results in Combinatorial Number Theory*, Enseign. Math. (2), vol. 28, Enseignement Math., Geneva, 1980.
- [2] J. Fang and Y. Chen, *On a conjecture of Erdős, Graham and Spencer, II*, Discrete Appl. Math. 156 (2008), 2950-2958.
- [3] C. Sándor, *On a problem of Erdős*, J. Number Theory 63 (1997), 203-210.
- [4] S. Guo, *A counterexample to a conjecture of Erdős, Graham and Spencer*, Electron. J. Comb. 15 (2008), #N43, 3 pp.
- [5] Y. Chen, *On a conjecture of Erdős, Graham and Spencer*, J. Number Theory 119 (2006), 307-314.